

A. Safety Dimensions (RQ1)

Themes	Subthemes	Definitions	Examples
A.1 Asset security	A.1.1 Security of gambling funds (cash)	Whether cash used for gambling remains safe, intact, and under control, without being lost, stolen.	Safety means no theft, no robbery, and no exposure to laundered funds.
	A.1.2 Security of casino chips	Whether casino chips remain safe, intact, and under control, without being lost, stolen, exchanged unfairly, or manipulated.	When chips vanish due to dealer manipulation, it transcends ordinary gameplay loss.
	A.1.3 Security of personal belongings	Whether personal belongings and valuables, such as bags, phones, wallets, or jewelry, remain safe, intact, and free from loss, theft, or damage in the casino.	If your mobile phone, wallet, and other valuables are not stolen, then you are considered safe.
A.2 Data S&P	A.2.1 S&P of surveillance footage	Whether video footage captured by casino surveillance systems is securely stored and used in ways that protect gamblers from unauthorized access, disclosure, misuse, or harmful exposure.	The fact that a security camera captured me entering a casino means that the security of that data is also a form of security.
	A.2.2 S&P of personal identification information	Whether personal identity-related information collected by the casino, such as name, ID number, or contact details, is protected from unauthorized collection, access, sharing, or misuse.	If someone were to use my personal information to apply for a loan, it would not only violate my privacy but also put me in an unsafe situation
	A.2.3 S&P of membership application logs	Whether records generated during casino membership application or use are securely handled and protected from unauthorized access, disclosure, tracking, or misuse.	When a casino asks you to sign up for a membership card, they usually require you to provide information, right? Providing that information to them might not be very safe.
A.3 Psychological safety	A.3.1 Self-control	Whether the gambler is able to regulate their own gambling behavior, including stopping in time, limiting spending, and avoiding impulsive or excessive betting.	The key is to be able to control yourself and stop at the appropriate time, so as not to act impulsively and lose control.

	A.3.2 Emotional stability	Whether the gambler can maintain a stable emotional state during gambling, without being driven into distress, panic, anger, frustration, or emotional loss of control.	I am aware that gambling addiction can lead to serious consequences, especially psychological distress, such as extreme thoughts, impulsivity, and irritability. Therefore, maintaining a calm mindset and avoiding addiction is also a manifestation of safety
A.4 Physical safety	A.4.1 Protection from bodily harm	Whether the gambler's body remains free from physical injury, assault, or other direct bodily harm in the casino environment.	Physical safety refers to any situation in which medical attention may be required, such as injury during disputes or facing dangerous scenarios that threaten health.

B. Adversaries (RQ2)

Themes	Subthemes	Definitions	Examples
B.1 Casino operators	/	The casino as an organization, including its management and internal systems that make decisions, control operations, or handle user data.	The casino manages these gaming machines; we have no way of knowing if they have secretly adjusted the settings.
B.2 Dealers	/	Casino staff who directly manage or assist gambling activities at game tables.	I've seen news about dealers conspiring with gamblers to rig games—if I were their opponent, I'd be at a serious disadvantage.
B.3 Hackers	/	External malicious actors who may try to steal, access, or misuse casino or gambler data through technical means.	Skilled hackers could breach firewalls and use my data to apply for loans.
B.4 Cloud service providers	/	External companies that may store, process, or manage casino data through cloud-based systems or services.	The casino is government-certified, but service providers are not. We do not even know where our data is stored, nor whether it might be sold.
B.5 Other gamblers	/	Other casino patrons whose actions may create risks, such as theft, harassment, cheating, or unwanted attention.	I have no idea who might be in the casino - there could be individuals intent on theft or robbery, or after significant losses, they could become irrational

and resort to extreme actions.

C. Threats (RQ3)

Themes	Subthemes	Definitions	Examples
C.1 [Threats to asset security] Game manipulation	C.1.1 Casino operators manipulating ETG/EGM	Concerns that casino operators may secretly manipulate ETG/EGM, affecting game fairness.	Casinos definitely set thresholds for when the jackpot hits based on accumulated bets.
	C.1.2 Dealers manipulating dice shaker/card shuffler	Concerns that dealers may secretly manipulate dice shaker/card shuffler, affecting game fairness.	Only the dealers have access to those devices. Even if they take hands off during the roll, they still open the lid. If magnets were used to change dice orientation, we'd never know.
C.2 [Threats to asset security] Theft	C.2.1 Other gamblers stealing chips	Concerns that other gamblers may steal casino chips.	Betting at a crowded table with lots of people watching can actually be pretty risky, because someone might take advantage of the chaos. They may pretend they are just placing a bet, but then quickly steal your chips.
	C.2.2 Other gamblers stealing cash/other valuable personal belongings	Concerns that other gamblers may steal cash/other valuable personal belongings.	I'm also worried that some random people in the casino might steal things, especially when you're focused on the game and not paying close attention to your phone or other belongings.
C.3 [Threats to asset security] Illegal activities	C.3.1 Receiving laundered money when exchanging currency with other gamblers	Concerns that other gamblers may encourage participation in illegal activities, such as money laundering, via online transfers.	I was in a rush to leave Macao, so I exchanged money with these people, only to find myself caught in a money laundering scheme.
C.4 [Threats to data S&P] Identity theft	C.4.1 Hackers stealing identities for loan or illegal gambling	Concerns that personal identity information has been stolen by hackers for illegal online financial lending.	Skilled hackers could breach firewalls and use my data to apply for loans.

and misuse			
C.5 [Threats to data S&P] Gambling records disclosure	C.5.1 Cloud service providers selling data	Concerns that cloud service providers may sell gambling records to employers or banks, damaging personal reputation and credibility.	Even if I don't tell anyone I went, the messages and the cameras already know. It's like the system keeps a record of everything I do. It would be very troublesome if this data were sold by the data storage provider.
C.6 [Threats to psychological safety] Gambling addiction	C.6.1 Casino operators intensifying visual effects	Concerns that casino operators may encourage addictive behaviour through ETG/EGM animations, sound effects, and lighting, as well as the membership welfare policies.	These machines feel addictive, you sit down and can't get up. The flashy animations keep pulling you in, making you continuously put in more money.
C.7 [Threats to physical safety] Violent incidents	C.7.1 Other gamblers causing violent incidents	Concerns over conflicts instigated by other gamblers escalating into violent incidents and causing physical injury.	I once played at a table where some players looked intimidating, like gang members. In several rounds, our bets were in direct opposition, and I kept winning. They left visibly furious, and I was afraid they might attack me — or even wait outside the casino to retaliate.

D. Protective Strategies (RQ4)

Themes	Subthemes	Definitions	Examples
D.1 Casino defenses	D.1.1 Applying round-the-clock surveillance	Casinos implement continuous monitoring through security cameras and surveillance systems to deter illicit activities and enhance gamblers' sense of safety.	No matter the angle, there is always a camera capturing everything; it essentially signals to wrongdoers that they are being constantly watched.
	D.1.2 Replacing human-operated tasks with	Casinos integrate digital devices, such as automatic card shufflers, to reduce human error and ensure fair play, thereby reinforcing gamblers'	Games controlled by machines, and the dealer is unable to manipulate the outcome because they lack insight into the inner workings of the dealing

	digital devices	trust.	system.
D.2 Personal mitigation strategies	D.2.1 Adopting “big fish” psychological comfort	Offering psychological cues, reassuring oneself as an insignificant retail gambler schemers would ignore.	Only those with a transaction volume of tens of millions of Hong Kong dollars might actually attract the casino’ s scrutiny.
	D.2.2 Betting under probability assessment	Analyzing game history to calculate banker/player win probabilities, ensuring the distribution of winning rates aligns with theoretical equilibrium.	That day was odd—the dice kept landing on similar numbers. Suspecting a machine fault, I stopped betting and began checking the scoreboard data, which I had never done before since I used to pick tables randomly.
	D.2.3 Anonymizing identities	Avoiding membership registration to reduce traceable records of gambling activities.	I’ d rather give up the benefits of membership than provide them with more personal information. I'm willing to sacrifice perks—I won't risk any decision that's not worthwhile.
	D.2.4 Locking liquidity	Carrying only cash within budget, avoiding bank cards, skipping mobile banking apps, and setting up fixed-term deposits to cut off liquid funds temporarily.	The best solution is simply having no money. I lock up my funds and only bring a limited amount of cash.
	D.2.5 Blocking gambling environment	Applying for self-exclusion (e.g., casino ban) to remove triggers; deliberately destroying Visa cards and avoiding cities with legal gambling.	My last resort was to remove my visa — I will no longer go to Macao. If I can still enter, I’ ll keep thinking about it.
	D.2.6 Do nothing	Once inside the casino, disregard all precautions and take no measures.	There’ s nothing I can do; control is entirely with the casinos.